

Donkey Republic

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Donkey Republic is bike-share startup geared to improve mobility in urban areas. Using its proprietary smart lock, the company offers shared bikes (Donkeys) to commuters, urban residents and tourists in the palm of their hands.

The fundamental disruption Donkey Republic brings to the already ~1million large bike share market is financial sustainability without (public) subsidies and no need for permits from authorities to start operations. Donkey Republic focuses on bringing bike share back to basics and keep the cost of both the bikes and the sharing technology on the bikes to a minimum.

Donkey Republic aims to provide a global service with a single global brand. It aims to achieve this by not only providing the technology to operate, but also the know-how and operational experience in procuring, maintaining and redistributing bicycles. We will manage each of these with utmost support of our IT platform and crowdsourcing and outsourcing to local partners where possible.

Donkey Republic offers simple, convenient and financially self-sustainable shared bikes. At the center of our solution is a smart lock that is mounted on Donkey bikes, which are operated by Donkey Apps.

Users are able to find, reserve and rent bicycles via their Donkey App. They will use the same App and single registration for any city with Donkey operations (as with Uber). In order to sign up with Donkey Republic, users will download the free Donkey App to their smartphone. They will need to define payment method and agree to our terms of service. One critical condition is that users will be penalized an amount which will be blocked on their payment card, if they do not return the bicycles.

Shops with service agreement will maintain donkey bikes. Redistribution of Donkeys will prioritize reliance on user community via incentives, and if this is not enough, will be outsourced to businesses that have idle capacity for moving bicycles around.

Donkey systems will grow globally via franchise operators. However, from customers point of view, the service standard and the brand providing the service does not change.